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DJECA KAO AKTIVNI ČIMBENICI GOSPODARSKOG RAZVOJA I PRAVNO ODREĐENJE NJIHOVA POLOŽAJA KROZ POVIJEST

Od najstarijeg doba djeca su kao članovi obitelji bili tihi subjekti gospodarstva. U samim začecima njihov je položaj određivan posredno ili, u manjoj mjeri neposredno, običajima i odredbama koje su propisivale obveze i odgovornost koju su imali ne samo kao članovi obitelji (pomoć i skrb o nemoćnima za samostalno privređivanje) već i članovi društva (budući vojni i porezni obveznici, odnosno njihovi roditelji). Skrb o bolesnim i starim roditeljima, zaštita te pomoć i sudjelovanje u osiguravanju materijalne egzistencije obitelji, preuzimanje obiteljskih (očinskih) zanata kao nastavak profesije – osiguranje novog naraštaja strateški bitne radne i ratne snage, bili su dio „državne politike“ te način organizacije reda u poredcima koji tu skrb nisu poznavali kao institucionaliziranu. S vremenom, a osobito nakon 1. industrijske revolucije, neke od ovih obveza preuzele su formalne institucije, ali samo nekolicina si ih je mogli priuštiti, dok su obveze djece prerasle u radnu obvezu koja je kao teško breme davala svoj obol ekonomskom razvoju. To breme bit će zbačeno pozitivnopravnom afirmacijom ljudskih prava općenito, odnosno specifičnih nedjeljivih i komplementarnih prava djece, a posebice pomicanjem dobnih granica koje osobu određuje kao dijete. Kao jedna od najranjivijih skupina, djeca su sudjelovala u gospodarskom razvoju, koji se razvojem prava djece transformirao, pa ga danas, i dalje u svjetlu daljnje potrebe poboljšanja prava djece, pratimo u drugačijem obličju.

Ključne riječi: prava djeteta, osobna prava, socijalna prava, ekonomska prava.

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CHILDREN AS ACTIVE FACTORS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND LEGAL REGULATION OF THEIR POSITION THROUGH HISTORY

From the earliest times, children as members of the family have been silent participants in the economy. At the very beginning, their position was determined either indirectly or, to a lesser extent, directly by customs and regulations that prescribed the obligations and responsibilities they had not only as family members (assistance and care for those unable to earn a living independently) but also as members of society (future soldiers and tax payers, or parents). Care for sick and elderly parents, protection and assistance and participation in ensuring the material existence of the family, taking over family (paternal) crafts as a continuation of the profession, and ensuring a new generation of strategically important labor and military power were part of "state policy" and a way of solving those problems in societies that did not recognize institutionalized forms of care. Over time, and especially after the First Industrial Revolution, some of these obligations were taken over by formal institutions, but only a few of them could afford such care, while children's obligations grew into work obligation which, as a heavy burden, contributed to the economic development. This heavy burden was lifted by the positive law affirmation of human rights in general and the specific indivisible and complementary rights of children, and particularly by delineating the age limits that define a person as a child. As one of the most vulnerable groups, children participated in economic development, which was transformed by the development of children's rights. Nowadays, in light of the need to improve children's rights protection, economic development is pursued in a different form.

Keywords: children's rights, personal rights, social rights, economic rights.